

Using Simplexes To Verify Existence Of Isometry For Map Keeping Distance One From The d -Dimensional Rational Space To It Self

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Abstract

As is known, every unit- distance-preserving mapping from Q^d into Q^d is an isometry provided $d \geq 5$. (The rational analogues of Beckman- Quarles theorem, due to W.hibi [8], [9]).The proof was based on the fact that has been proven: an auxiliary Lemma which ensures that: $\dim(\text{aff}(L[d])) = d$, For all the dimensions $d, d \geq 5$. When $L[d]$ the set of $4 \cdot \binom{d}{2}$ Points in Q^d in which precisely two non-zero coordinates are equal to $1/2$ or $-1/2$. Here, in this paper, we are going to prove the same result using the fact (due to J.Zaks [11]), that every mapping from Q^d into Q^d that preserves the distances 1 and $\sqrt{2}$ is an isometry, provided $d \geq 5$.

Introduction

A map $\varphi: (X, d_1) \rightarrow (Y, d_2)$, is called c - distance preserving, ($0 < c \in R$), if for all x, y in (X, d_1) , from $d_1(x, y) = c$, implies that $d_2(\varphi(x), \varphi(y)) = c$, furthermore, if the map saves all the distance $c > 0$ then φ is an isometry.

In general we denote by $\omega(d)$ to the clique number of the graph that has Q^d as its set of vertices, and two vertices x and y are connected by edge if and only if $\|x - y\| = 1$.

New result:

Theorem:

If d is a natural number and $d \geq 5$, then every unit-distance preserving mapping: $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^d$ is an isometry.

To prove Theorem 1, we will prove first the following auxiliary Theorem:

Auxiliary Theorem:

If $d \geq 5$, and if Z, W are any two points in Q^d , for which $\|Z - W\| = \sqrt{2}$, then there exists a finite set M_d , contains Z and W such that for every unit-distance preserving mapping

$f: M_d \rightarrow Q^d$, the following equality holds:

$$\|f(Z) - f(W)\| = \|Z - W\|.$$

To prove the auxiliary Theorem, we need the following auxiliary known Lemmas:

Known Lemmas:

We need the following Lemmas for our proofs to the main Theorem and to the auxiliary Theorem.

Lemma 1: (due J.Zaks [10]).

If $v_1, \dots, v_n, w_1, \dots, w_m$ are points in Q^d , $n \leq m$ such that:

$\|v_i - v_j\| = \|w_r - w_s\|$, for all, $1 \leq i \leq j \leq n$, $1 \leq r \leq s \leq m$, then there exists a congruence $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^d$, such that $f(v_i) = w_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq n$.

Lemma 2: (due to Chilakamarri [2]).

a. For even d , $\omega(d) = d+1$, if $d+1$ is a complete square; otherwise $\omega(d) = d$.

b. For odd d , $d \geq 5$, the value of $\omega(d)$ is as follows: if $d = 2n^2 - 1$, then $\omega(d) = d+1$; if $d \neq 2n^2 - 1$ and the Diophantine equation $dx^2 - 2(d-1)y^2 = z^2$ has a solution in which $x \neq 0$ then $\omega(d) = d$; otherwise $\omega(d) = d - 1$.

Lemma 3: (due W.hibi [4]).

If x and y are two points in Q^d , $d \geq 5$, so that:

$$\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} - 1 \leq \|x - y\| \leq \sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} + 1$$

Where $\omega(d) = m$, then a finite set $S(x,y)$ exists, contains x and y such that $f(x) \neq f(y)$ holds for every unit- distance preserving mapping $f: S(x,y) \rightarrow Q^d$.

Corollary from lemma 3: (due W.hibi [4]).

If x and y are two points in Q^d , $d \geq 5$, such that $\|x-y\| = \sqrt{2}$, then every unit- distance preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^d$ satisfies $f(x) \neq f(y)$.

Proof of Auxiliary Theorem:

Let $d \geq 5$, and let $\omega(d) = m$, then by Lemma 2, implies that $d - 1 \leq m \leq d + 1$.

Let Z, W are any two points in Q^d , for which $\|Z - W\| = \sqrt{2}$. We obtain the following assertions:

Case (a):

If d is odd, consider the $d - 1$ points $\{A_1, \dots, A_{d-1}\}$, defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, \frac{1}{2}, 0\right) \\ A_2 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}, 0\right) \\ A_3 &= \left(0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots, 0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, 0\right) \\ A_4 &= \left(0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0\right) \\ &\vdots \\ A_{d-2} &= \left(0, 0, \dots, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \dots, 0, 0, 0\right) \\ A_{d-1} &= \left(0, 0, \dots, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \dots, 0, 0, 0\right) \end{aligned}$$

The points $\{A_1, \dots, A_{d-1}\}$ form the vertices of a regular $(d - 2)$ - simplex of edge length one in Q^d . Let the $d - 1$ points B_1, B_2, \dots, B_{d-1} of Q^d , be defined by $B_i = -A_i$, simplex of edge length one in Q^d .

Let T_d defined by $T_d = \{A_1, \dots, A_{d-1}, B_1, \dots, B_{d-1}\}$.

Fix a $k, 1 \leq k \leq d - 1$ by Lemma 1 and based on $\|Z - W\| = \|A_k - B_k\|$ there exists a rational congruence h for which $h(A_k) = Z := A_k^*$ and $h(B_k) = W := B_k^*$; denote $h(A_i) = A_i^*$ and $h(B_i) = B_i^*$ for all $1 \leq i \leq d - 1$.

Let $T_d^* = \{A_1^*, \dots, A_{d-1}^*, B_1^*, \dots, B_{d-1}^*\}$; it is clear that $Z, W \in T_d^*$.

Denote the set $M_d = S(A_1^*, B_1^*) \cup S(A_2^*, B_2^*) \cup \dots \cup S(A_{d-1}^*, B_{d-1}^*)$, where the $S(A_i^*, B_i^*)$ for $1 \leq i \leq d - 1$, are given by Lemma 3.

We wish to remark that the distance $\sqrt{2}$ between A_i^* and B_i^* is within the two bounds:

$$\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} - 1, \text{ and } \sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} + 1, \text{ where } \omega(d) = m, \text{ which needs not be } d-1, \text{ as } T_d^* \text{ may incorrectly indicate.}$$

Let $f, f: M_d \rightarrow Q^d$ be any unit-distance preserving mapping.

Claim 1.a:

If x and y are two points in T_d^* , then $f(x) \neq f(y)$.

Proof of Claim 1.a:

Computing the mutual distances of the points in T_d^* shows that:

$$\begin{aligned} \|A_i^* - A_j^*\| &= \|B_i^* - B_j^*\| = \|A_i^* - B_j^*\| = 1, \text{ for all } 1 \leq i \leq j \leq d - 1, \text{ and} \\ \|A_i^* - B_i^*\| &= \sqrt{2}, \text{ for all } 1 \leq i \leq d - 1. \end{aligned}$$

All of the distances above are between $\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} - 1$, and $\sqrt{2 + \frac{2}{m-1}} + 1$.

Therefore, $\|x - y\| = 1$ then $\|f(x) - f(y)\| = 1$, hence $f(x) \neq f(y)$, if $\|x - y\| = \sqrt{2}$, there is an $i, 1 \leq i \leq d - 1$ such that $x = A_i^*, y = B_i^*$; and $\|A_i^* - B_i^*\| = \sqrt{2}$.

By Lemma 3, applied to A_i^* ; and B_i^* , there exists a set $S(A_i^*, B_i^*)$, that contains A_i^* ; and B_i^* , for which every unit-distance preserving mapping $g: S(A_i^*, B_i^*) \rightarrow Q^d$, satisfies

$$g(A_i^*) \neq g(B_i^*).$$

In particular, this holds for the mapping $g = f/S(A_i^*, B_i^*)$, therefore $f(A_i^*) \neq f(B_i^*)$.

Claim 2.a:

The mapping f preserves all the distance $\sqrt{2}$, between A_i^* and B_i^* for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, d - 1$. In particular $\|f(Z) - f(W)\| = \sqrt{2}$.

Proof of Claim 2.a:

Consider the following $(d - 3)$ points:

$$\Delta_1 = \{f(A_3^*), f(B_4^*), \dots, f(B_{d-1}^*)\}$$

All of their mutual distances are one, since f preserves distance one, so they form the vertices of a regular $(d - 4)$ - simplex of edge length one in Q^d . The intersection of the $(d - 3)$ -unit spheres which are centered at the vertices of this simplex, is a 3- sphere of radius

$$t_{d-3} = \sqrt{\frac{d-2}{2(d-3)}}, \text{ centered at the center } O_1 \text{ of } \Delta_1; \text{ let } S_{(O_j, t)}^3 \text{ denote this 3- sphere.}$$

Let Δ_2 and Δ_3 be defined by:

$$\Delta_2 = \{f(A_4^*), f(B_3^*), f(\hat{B}_4^*), f(B_5^*) \dots, f(B_{d-1}^*)\}, \text{ and}$$

$$\Delta_3 = \{f(A_5^*), f(B_3^*), f(B_4^*), f(\hat{B}_5^*), f(B_6^*) \dots, f(B_{d-1}^*)\}.$$

In the similar way we obtain the two 3- spheres $S_{(O_2, t)}^3$ and $S_{(O_3, t)}^3$, having their centers at O_2 and O_3 , which are the centers of Δ_2 and Δ_3 respectively.

The four points $f(A_1^*), f(A_2^*), f(B_1^*)$ and $f(B_2^*)$ are in the intersection of the three 3-spheres $S_{(O_j, t)}^3$, $j = 1, 2, 3$.

By Claim 1.a, the three simplexes Δ_1, Δ_2 and Δ_3 are different, even though any two of the have many vertices in common.

We will prove that $O_1 \neq O_2 \neq O_3$:

Assume that $O_1 = O_2 := O$. (See Figure 1).

It follows that $\|f(B_j^*) - O\| = \|f(A_i^*) - O\| = t$, $3 \leq i \leq 4$ and $j = 3, 4, \dots, d - 1$.

In particular, the point O the center of the simplex $\{f(B_3^*), f(B_4^*), \dots, f(B_{d-1}^*)\}$, so

$$O = \frac{1}{d-3} (f(B_3^*) + \dots + f(B_{d-1}^*)), \text{ but the point } O \text{ is also the center of the simplex } \Delta_1 \text{ so}$$

$$O = \frac{1}{d-3} (f(A_3^*) + f(B_4^*) + \dots + f(B_{d-1}^*)).$$

It follows that $f(A_3^*) = f(B_3^*)$, a contradiction to Claim 1.a, thus $O_1 \neq O_2$. In a similar way we obtain that $O_1 \neq O_2 \neq O_3$; moreover, the three points O_1, O_2 and O_3 are finely independent since they lie in a sphere of radius $r = \|O_i - M\|$, $i = 1, 2, 3$ centered at M where M is the center of the simplex $\{f(B_5^*), \dots, f(B_{d-1}^*)\}$. (See Figure 2).

Figure 2

Therefore the three 3- spheres $S_{(0_j,t)}^3, j = 1,2,3$ are different, they have the same radius

$t_{d-3} = \sqrt{\frac{d-2}{2(d-3)}}$ and have a non-empty intersection; hence these three 3- spheres intersect in a one-dimensional sphere, which is a circle.

Thus $f(A_1^*), f(A_2^*), f(B_1^*),$ and $f(B_2^*)$ form the vertex set of a quadrangle, of edge length one, that lies in a circle. (See Figure 3).

Figure 3

The situations A and B are impossible since $f(A_i^*) \neq f(B_i^*)$ for $i = 1,2$.

It follows that $f(A_1^*), f(A_2^*), f(B_1^*)$, and $f(B_2^*)$ form the vertex set of a square in a circle of diameter $\sqrt{2}$, implying:

$$|f(A_1^*) - f(B_1^*)| = |f(A_2^*) - f(B_2^*)| = \sqrt{2} \text{ Since } f(A_i^*) \neq f(B_i^*) \text{ for } i = 1, 2.$$

It follows by Lemma 1 that the mapping f preserves the distance $\sqrt{2}$, between A_i^* and B_i^* , for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, d-1$. In particular $|f(Z) - f(W)| = \sqrt{2}$.

Case (b):

If d is even:

Consider the d points $\{A_1, \dots, A_d\}$, defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, \frac{1}{2}, 0\right) \\ A_2 &= \left(\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}\right) \\ A_3 &= \left(0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots, 0, \frac{1}{2}, 0\right) \\ A_4 &= \left(0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, \dots, 0, -\frac{1}{2}, 0\right) \\ &\vdots \\ A_{d-1} &= \left(0, 0, \dots, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \dots, 0, 0\right) \\ A_d &= \left(0, 0, \dots, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \dots, 0, 0\right) \end{aligned}$$

The points $\{A_1, \dots, A_d\}$ form the vertices of a regular $(d-1)$ -simplex of edge length one in Q^d . Let the d points B_1, B_2, \dots, B_d of Q^d defined by $B_i = -A_i$, $1 \leq i \leq d$, their mutual distances are one, so they form the vertices of a regular $(d-1)$ -simplex of edge length one in Q^d .

Let T_d defined by $T_d = \{A_1, \dots, A_d, B_1, \dots, B_d\}$.

Fix a k , $1 \leq k \leq d$, by Lemma 1 and based on $\|Z - W\| = \|A_k - B_k\|$ there exists a rational isometry h for which $h(A_k) = Z := A_k^*$ and $h(B_k) = W := B_k^*$; denote $h(A_i) = A_i^*$ and $h(B_i) = B_i^*$ for all $1 \leq i \leq d$.

Let $T_d^* = \{A_1^*, \dots, A_d^*, B_1^*, \dots, B_d^*\}$; it is clear that $Z, W \in T_d^*$.

Denote the set $M_d = S(A_1^*, B_1^*) \cup S(A_2^*, B_2^*) \cup \dots \cup S(A_d^*, B_d^*)$.

Let $f, f: M_d \rightarrow Q^d$ be any unit-distance preserving mapping.

Claim 1.b:

If x and y are two points in T_d^* , then $f(x) \neq f(y)$.

The proof of Claim 1.b is similar to these of Claim 1.a, hence omitted.

Claim 2.b:

The mapping f preserves all the distance $\sqrt{2}$, between A_i^* and B_i^* for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, d$ in particular $|f(Z) - f(W)| = \sqrt{2}$.

Proof of Claim 2:

Consider the following $(d-2)$ points:

$$\Delta_1 = \{f(A_3^*), f(B_4^*), \dots, f(B_d^*)\}$$

All of their mutual distances are one, since f preserves distance one, so they form the vertices of a regular $(d-3)$ -simplex of edge length one in Q^d . The intersection of the $(d-2)$ unit spheres, centered at the vertices of this simplex, is a 2- sphere of radius $t_{d-2} = \sqrt{\frac{d-1}{2(d-2)}}$, centered at the center O_1 of Δ_1 ; let $S_{(O_1, t)}^2$ denote this 2- sphere.

$$\Delta_2 = \{f(A_4^*), f(B_3^*), f(\hat{B}_4^*), f(B_5^*), \dots, f(B_6^*)\}$$

In the similar way we obtain the 2- spheres $S_{(O_2, t)}^2$, having her center at O_2 , which is also the center of Δ_2 .

The four points $f(A_1^*), f(A_2^*), f(B_1^*)$ and $f(B_2^*)$ are in the intersection of the two, 2- spheres $S_{(O_j, t)}^2$, $j = 1, 2$.

By Claim 1.b, the two simplexes Δ_1 , and Δ_2 are different, but they have many vertices in common. By using arguments, similar to those that appeared in the proof of Claim 2.a we obtain that $O_1 \neq O_2$. Therefore these two 2- spheres are different, they have the same radius

$t_{d-2} = \sqrt{\frac{d-1}{2(d-2)}}$ and they have a non-empty intersection. It follows that these two 2- spheres intersect in a one-dimensional sphere, which is a circle.

Thus $f(A_1^*), f(A_2^*), f(B_1^*),$ and $f(B_2^*)$ form the vertex set of a quadrangle, of edge length one, that lies in a circle. (See Figure 3).

It follows as the previous case that $f(A_1^*), f(A_2^*), f(B_1^*),$ and $f(B_2^*)$ form the vertex set of a square in a circle of diameter $\sqrt{2}$, implying:

$$|f(A_1^*) - f(B_1^*)| = |f(A_2^*) - f(B_2^*)| = \sqrt{2} \text{ Since } f(A_i^*) \neq f(B_i^*) \text{ for } i = 1, 2.$$

It follows by Lemma 1 that the mapping f preserves the distance $\sqrt{2}$ between A_i^* and B_i^* for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, d - 1$. In particular $|f(Z) - f(W)| = \sqrt{2}$.

This completes the proof of the Auxiliary Theorem.

Proof of the main Theorem:

Let d be a natural number, $d \geq 5$ and let f be a unit distance-preserving mapping $f: Q^d \rightarrow Q^d$. By the Auxiliary Theorem, the unit distance-preserving mapping f preserves the distance $\sqrt{2}$. Our result follows by using a Theorem (due. Zaks [11]), which states that if a mapping $g: Q^d \rightarrow Q^d$ preserves the distance 1 and $\sqrt{2}$, then g is an isometry, provides $d \geq 5$.

This completes the proof of the main Theorem.

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